

INTERACTIVE MUSIC SCORE COMPLETION

Dr. Grégory Beller
HfMT Hamburg
gregory.beller
@hfmt-hamburg.de

Prof. Dr. Jacob Sello
HfMT Hamburg
jacob.sello
@hfmt-hamburg.de

Prof. Dr. Georg Hajdu
HfMT Hamburg
georg.hajdu
@hfmt-hamburg.de

Prof. Thomas Görne
HAW Hamburg
thomas.goerne
@haw-hamburg.de

ABSTRACT

The autocompletion paradigm is applied to computer-aided music composition. Integrated in an interactive score editor prototype, a data-driven model is trained on an initial corpus defined by the composer. When the completion function is called, the model suggests possible continuations of musical phrases by superimposing them on the score. The user can then choose or avoid a quotation from the corpus, then modify it. Based on an interactive and online automatic learning, the modifications made, once validated, are reinserted in the learning corpus. Progressively, the completion suggestions are more and more personalized, according to the curatorial and editorial choices made by the composer. The score editor becomes a personal companion of the composer in classical tasks such as composition, harmonization, arrangement and orchestration.

1. INTRODUCTION

Computer-Aided Algorithmic Composition (CAAC) covers several topics such as score analysis, transformation, interpolation, generation, orchestration, arrangement and human-computer improvisation (co-improvisation). In this paper, CAAC is used for score writing in melody generation, arrangement and orchestration tasks. After this introduction are presented different methods for automatic score generation, based on categories (author, style or emotion), on the interpolation of two or more given score fragments or on an improvisation model learned online. Then an original method based on the auto-completion of scores from a similarity search in a corpus is introduced, that evolves according to the curatorial choices made by the user. This method is based on the design of a reinforcement learning paradigm that integrates online the curatorial choices made by the user to the learning base. Finally, a prototype of a score editor based on the auto-completion of musical fragments from an interactive corpus is presented. Two real cases of use of this prototype in the context of music composition are presented in order to open a discussion. Future developments are presented in conclusion.

2. AUTOMATIC SCORE GENERATION

In automatic score generation, an input command defining a specific target category ("in the Latin musical style", "in the Mozart style", "in D sharp and 4/4", "gives a sad mood") is used to generate an original score piece. The generation of original scores in a given mood, musical style (DeepJazz¹) or composer's style (MuseNet²) has become popular in recent years. Algorithms, labs, and brands (Google Magenta, OpenAI MuseNet, Sony Flow Machines) compete [1] and new competitive market sectors are emerging such as generative music for wellness (AmperMusic³) or for video games (AIVA⁴).

From the beginning of CAAC to the recent advances of deep learning, computer and machine learning have been used to compose Bach-like chorales. From the famous "Illiad suite" [2], Experimental Musical Intelligence - EMI [3], reinforcement learning [4], time series RNN [5], graphical model [6] and the Transformer [7], a sequence model based on self-attention that maintains long-range coherence in music generation [8], have been used to generate chorales which sound like written by J.S. Bach. The EBMS⁵ (Emotion-based Music Synthesizer) is a pseudo-random music generator controlled by emotions ("sad", "anger", "happy"). Designed to produce music that signifies a particular emotion, it is used in neuroscientific research to generate musical control stimuli [9].

It is also possible to generate a score by interpolation of two given scores. Georg Hajdu's opera "Der Sprung – Beschreibung einer Oper17" (1999) uses a neural network to guide the melodic interpolations in one of the scenes [10]. Annie Dorsen's performance Yesterday Tomorrow⁶ takes us on a musical interpolation journey based on evolutionary algorithms. Infinite Sun⁷ is an artwork dealing with "Artificial Spirituality", where eleven generative musical agents sing continuously real-time generated spiritual songs made of the multiple cross interpolations of well-known spiritual songs

¹ <https://deepjazz.io/>

² <https://openai.com/blog/musenet/>

³ <https://www.ampermusic.com>

⁴ <https://www.aiva.ai>

⁵ <http://www.gregbeller.com/2013/02/ebms/>

⁶ <http://www.gregbeller.com/2015/06/yesterday-tomorrow/>

⁷ <http://www.gregbeller.com/2019/03/infinitesun/>

selected in various cultures and transcribed in the language of a singing synthesizer. MusicVAE [11] learns a latent space of musical scores and randomly samples from the prior distribution and interpolates between existing sequences for several pre-trained MusicVAE models.

Another approach in automatic score generation can be seen as an interpolation between what is played and what has been previously played or learned by the machine. The human-machine improvisation (co-improvisation) allows the musical conversation between an instrumentalist and the machine [12]. The latter listens to the musician's playing, models the musical discourse in real time and generates musically interesting responses. Some models can be trained on online data or presented a priori, in order to extend the machine's repertoire beyond the improvisation situation [13]. Factor oracles [14], augmented Markov models [15], and neural networks [16] learn in realtime and let you play a duet with the computer.

When the instrument is not midi, an audio-midi transcription step is necessary. This is the basis of sound-guided approaches, such as Orchidea⁸ that allows automatic orchestration from a sound target.

3. SCORE-COMPLETION AS AN AUTHORIZING TOOL

Line/word completion is a feature that allows an application to predict the continuation of a line or word that the user is typing. In text-based interfaces, users can typically press the tab key to accept a suggestion. Some autocompletion algorithms learn new words after the user has written them several times, and can suggest personalized choices based on observation of the user's habits. The classical algorithms in the text auto completion task, such as Prefix Query or N-Gram, are replaced here by the minimization of the K-NN distance of the fragment to be completed with the corpus, especially because in the case of music, the note sequence may not be quite the same. This algorithm, by its simplicity, allows us to evaluate the interest of the auto-complete approach for composition. It can be replaced by any machine learning algorithm allowing to generate an extension of a musical phrase according to its context.

Our motivations to apply the auto-completion paradigm in the field of computer-aided composition are the following. Autocompletion can be used as a creative tool, a source of inspiration or a way to "compare" the entered scores. Suggested continuations can be seen as surprises and inspire the composer to generate new material. As a pedagogical tool, contextual information related to the

proposed citation can be displayed. In a complementary way, by antagonistic use, the composer can avoid quoting previously written fragments, and thus ensure the originality of the work. Finally, a musical similarity engine integrated to a score editor that takes into account the modifications made by the user can become a companion tool assisting the daily task of composition. In the long run, in the elaboration of a set of works with this assistant, a model of curatorial choices is elaborated by the composer who shapes recurrent elements of the musical discourse.

4. LEARNING OF THE USER'S CURATORIAL CHOICES

Exploring interaction possibilities by means of reinforcement learning leads to assisted Interactive machine learning [17]. Reinforcement learning is a machine learning training method based on rewarding desired behaviors and/or punishing undesired ones. Indirectly changing the statistical weights of a model by rewarding its result can be a laborious task for the user. Our approach consists in reinjecting into the learning corpus results selected and edited by the user, in order to update the model as it is used.

A model is trained on an initial corpus of score fragments. Then, as new fragments are generated by the model, selected, manipulated and edited by the user, the resulting fragments are incorporated into the (feedback) learning corpus. The interactive aspect is based on the relative immediacy of the learning phase or its re-actualization, which is computed after each user's return. Metaphorically, a large temporal window of a finite observable memory of musical fragments slides in as the user interacts (see Figure 1). The more feedback the user gives, the more the model "forgets" its initial corpus to evolve into a new corpus shaped by the user.

Fig. 1. Design of interactive machine learning showing the two actions of the user.

Figure 1 shows the two actions of the user. On the left, "User input 1" is a note insertion which requires a score-completion. A continuation is inferred by the generative model. On the right, "User input 2" is the

⁸ <https://forum.ircam.fr/projects/detail/orchidea/>

manual edition of the suggested score fragment. Once validated, the new fragment populates the training corpus which can then be reduced by one sample (or not). In the case of the simulation of a forgetfulness effect, as shown in Figure 1, the decrease can affect the oldest sample according to the indexing order (data index). In the case of the constitution of a corpus by appropriation of the initial material, the decrease can affect the sample closest to the last inferred fragment, so that the initial base is progressively personalized by the user.

5. INTERACTIVE SCORE EDITOR PROTOTYPE

The interactive editor for auto-completing musical scores has been developed in the Max⁹ programming environment and is based on the Maxscore [18], Bach and Cage libraries [19, 20].

Initial scores are segmented into fragments of variable length represented by feature vectors of numerical descriptors (duration, symbolic duration, index, voice, onset, symbolic onset, phase, measure, tempo, centroid, energy, spread, number of notes, rhythm distribution, chroma, number of lyrics...) and symbolic descriptors (title, path, lyrics, label...). The feature vectors are stored in an SQLite database. Snapshot queries allow the sub-selection of sets of fragments that are represented by a 2D scatter plot. Distances based on descriptor subsets allow to order the fragments by similarity. Figure 2 displays a prototype of a fragment management software.

Fig. 2. Prototype of a fragment management interface realized in Max thanks to the Cage library. On the upper left, the XML score file is imported and segmented. On the right, a 2D Scatter-plot allows for visualizing the fragment corpus along two descriptor axes (centroid and “number of notes”). On the lower left, a selected fragment displayed.

Composing with real-time corpus-based concatenative synthesis for symbolic notation allows for aggregating original score fragments in an interactive way. One can add fragments to an existing score by browsing the 2D Scatter-plot and select the most proximate point by minimizing a K-NN distance. It is also possible to

concatenate several segments in a metronomic way to create new rhythmic sequences, as it is the case in “Casual Causality”¹⁰. Other interactive writing modes depend on how the next element is selected and then written into the resulting score.

To score-complete a given musical fragment, the selection is made by hovering over the edited score. Each hovered note, described within its fragment, triggers the selection of a similar fragment. This similar fragment is aligned to the target note, displayed in transparency on the score and “printed” in the score after validation by the composer. The juxtaposition of the initial fragment with the most similar fragment produces a new fragment that can be modified before being inserted back into the database. The database is thus populated as the user interacts with the editor.

6. CASE STUDY: COMPOSING LIKE GESUALDO

In “GESULADO, eine Autopsie”¹¹, a five-voice choir sings some original madrigals but also original compositions including generated lyrics. Some vocal compositions are also delivered by a virtual choir made of synthetic voices thanks to the Max ISiS¹² singing synthesis software. A initial corpus of about fifty madrigals selected from the six Books of Madrigals for Five Voices of Carlo Gesualdo, is taken from IMSLP¹³ in an XML score file format. The choice of this format allows the conservation of the lyrics and other information not contained in the midi files. In the process of composing original pieces from existing fragments and as the interaction with the editor progresses, the corpus changes from pure fragments of Gesualdo’s madrigals to an unpublished set of fragments shaped by the composer. “Belta Tormenti” is an example of a composition written with the interactive score editor (see figure 3). It is an original madrigal made of modified Gesualdo’s fragments for four synthetic voices and one human soprano voice, premiered by Miri Rottmayer. This madrigal was generated from a subset of the training corpus corresponding to Books V and VI, during which chromaticism became more and more important in Carlo Gesualdo’s writing. An interesting aspect of this composition work is the automatic generation of the arrangement. By applying the auto-completion principle to the dominant melody (here the top soprano voice 1), the editor returns not only a possible completion but also the associated arrangement of the other four voices. Thus the editor can not only generate a melody but also propose arrangement or orchestration suggestions.

¹⁰ <http://www.gregbeller.com/2022/05/casual-causality/>

¹¹ <http://www.gregbeller.com/2021/01/gesualdo-eine-autopsie/>

¹² <https://forum.ircam.fr/projects/detail/max-isis/>

¹³ <https://imslp.org>

⁹ <https://cycling74.com/>

54

re La do - re La do - che
E al - sen - poi che
do - lo - po o poi
to cor, che tas - che
por - ta tor - men - che

Fig. 3. Last four bars of the score “Belta tormenti” composed using the interactive score editor. Recordings available on the project website.

For the composition of scenes 2 and 5 of the Opera "The Fault", created in January 2023, the author has explored a second use case starting from an initial corpus that he himself composed.

7. CONCLUSION

This article presents a prototype of a score editor whose generative part is based on the principle of auto-completion of musical fragments. In the context of music creation, autocompletion of musical phrases can be used as an inspiration tool, a browser for quoting melodic phrases or a checker of copyright-free themes. Embedded in a prototype interactive score editor, a generative model is trained on an initial corpus which can be defined according to the composer, the musical style, the mood or another defined categorisation. At each note insertion, the model suggests possible continuation of musical phrases by superimposing them on the score. The user can then interactively choose quotes from the initial corpus and modify them at will, while creating her/his own corpus of quotes, her/his own musical language. From imitation of style by musical quotation (bootstrap corpus) to the generation of new custom material based on user feedback (feedback corpus), the suggestions produced by the software become more and more personalized as the user interacts with the score editor. A prototype of an interactive score editor with automatic score completion was implemented and used in two concrete artistic contexts. Several avenues of evolution are now being considered, such as enriching the generative algorithm with deep networks or creating a more accessible web version.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is supported by the KiSS (Kinetics in Sound and Space) Program jointly organized by the University of Music and Drama (HfMT), Hamburg, Germany and the Hamburg University of Applied Sciences (HAW), Hamburg, Germany.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] C.-Z. A Huang, H. V Koops., E. Newton-Rex, Dinculescu M., C. J. Cai , “AI Song Contest: Human-AI Co-Creation in Songwriting”, arXiv, 2020.
- [2] L. Hiller, L. Isaacson, ”Experimental Music: Composition with an Electronic Computer”, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1959.
- [3] D. Cope, “Virtual music: Computer synthesis of musical style”, Cambridge, MIT Press, 2001.
- [4] A. Cont, S. Dubnov, G. Assayag, ”Anticipatory Model of Musical Style Imitation Using Collaborative and Competitive Reinforcement Learning”, SAB ABIALS, pp. 285-306, 2006.
- [5] F. Liang, “Bachbot: Automatic composition in the style of Bach chorales”, University of Cambridge, 2016.
- [6] G. Hadjeres, F. Pachet and F. Nielsen, “DeepBach: a Steerable Model for Bach Chorales Generation”, arXiv, 2017.
- [7] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, L. Kaiser, and I. Polosukhin, “Attention is all you need”, in Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, 2017
- [8] C.-Z. A. Huang, A. Vaswani, J. Uszkoreit, N. Shazeer, I. Simon, C. Hawthorne, A. M. Dai, M. D. Hoffman, M. Dinculescu and D. Eck, “Music Transformer”, arXiv, 2018.
- [9] I. Wollman, P. Arias, J.-J. Aucouturier, B. Morillon, “Neural entrainment to music is sensitive to melodic spectral complexity”, in Journal of Neurophysiology, American Physiological Society, 2020.
- [10] G. Hajdu, “Circularity in neural computation and its application to musical composition”, in ICMC, 1995.
- [11] A. Roberts, J. Engel, C. Raffel, C. Hawthorne, D. Eck, “A Hierarchical Latent Vector Model for Learning Long-Term Structure in Music”, ICML, arXiv:1803.05428, 2018.
- [12] G. Assayag, G. Bloch, M. Chemillier, A. Cont, S. Dubnov. “Omax Brothers: a Dynamic Topology of Agents for Improvisation Learning”, Workshop on Audio and Music Computing for Multimedia, ACM Multimedia, 2006.
- [13] K. Déguernel, E. Vincent, J. Nika, G. Assayag, K. Smaïli “Learning of Hierarchical Temporal Structures for Guided Improvisation”, in Computer Music Journal, MIT Press, 2019.
- [14] J. Nika, M. Chemillier, G. Assayag, “ImproteK: introducing scenarios into human-computer music improvisation”, ACM Computers in Entertainment, 2017.
- [15] F. Pachet, “The Continuator: Musical Interaction with Style”, in Journal of New Music Research, 2003
- [16] J.-P. Briot and G. Hadjeres, “Deep learning techniques for music generation - a survey”, arXiv:1709.01620, 2017.
- [17] Z. Chen and B. Liu, “Lifelong Machine Learning”, in Second Edition, vol. 12, no. 3. Morgan & Claypool Publishers, 2018.
- [18] N. Didkovsky and G. Hajdu, “MaxScore. Music notation in Max/MSP”, in Proceedings of the ICMC, 2008.
- [19] A. Agostini, D. Ghisi, “A Max Library for Musical Notation and Computer-Aided Composition”, in Computer Music Journal, Volume 39, No. 2, 2015, pp. 11–27
- [20] D. Ghisi, C. Agon, “Real-Time Corpus-Based Concatenative Synthesis for Symbolic Notation”, Proceedings of the TENOR conference, Cambridge, UK, 2016.